

Who Are the Liveaboards:

A Study in Bristol and Bath

Liisa Tuomi

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Abstract

Despite their increasing visibility, people who live on boats have not received an academic study of their lifestyle. A key question pertaining to the phenomenon of living aboard is why people do it and how does society perceive their lifestyle choice. This dissertation is intended to explore the social, cultural and economic circumstances in which 'live-aboards' have evolved. This study assesses how society confronts live-aboards and what is the importance of communal ties and consumerist values in their lives. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 14 live-aboards around Bristol and Bath. Data from the interviews was supported with field notes. The findings show that besides a lifestyle choice, living aboard can be a consequence of socioeconomic hardship. The findings verify that live-aboards encounter stereotypical thinking and discrimination from the sedentary society. Moreover, live-aboard lifestyle seem to be characterized by a sense of community and rejection of consumerist values. On this basis it is concluded that along with increasing the general awareness of live-aboards their community networks should be further supported.

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People who opt to live on boats instead of houses/apartments, often referred to as 'live-aboards', come from diverse social backgrounds. They are single dwellers, couples and whole families. For some it is as an ideal retirement lifestyle, whereas for others it presents an opportunity to own a home without having to finance an expensive mortgage (Lee and McDowall, 2003). There is no general accepted definition of live-aboards. What is more, the Government does not currently hold statistics on the number of people who live on boats. However, a study by the Association of Inland Navigation Authorities estimates that there are around 10,000-15,000 boats that are used for residential purposes. This could equate to approximately 20,000-45,000 live-aboards. However, estimates suggest there could be as few as 2,000 officially recognised residential moorings on Inland Waterways (ODPM, November 2005). If the amount of people living on their boats continues to increase, authorities will have to start providing more sites for live-aboards. Moreover, the increasing numbers of live-aboards suggest that in addition to economic arguments, there are social and cultural factors that underpin such lifestyle choices. To date, the literature on live-aboards has been focused on the practicalities of living afloat (Hiley, 1973 ; Lee and McDowall, 2003) but there is no sociological research on live-aboards which examines the social, cultural and economic issues surrounding this phenomena and the experiences of live-aboards per se.

This dissertation examines why people live on boats, their experiences of living aboard, and their perceptions of how they think the rest of the society perceives their lifestyle choice. Live-aboards or 'house-boaters' can get a distant reaction from the rest of the society, whether it comes from people 'higher in the hierarchy' or from institutions trying to curb the phenomenon. An often portrayed attitude towards live-aboards is to stereotype them and consequently perceive them as one group. Yet it should be emphasized that the participants in this project were treated individually and no attempt to simplify this group was made. My analysis of the lifestyles of live-aboards begins with an exploration of Inland Waterways, rising house prices and shortage of moorings. Following this, New Age Travellers (NATs) form a wider conceptual and theoretical springboard for this study, suggesting interesting if often misleading comparisons. It is hypothesized that live-aboards too are subject to stereotypical thinking and discriminatory policies. However, unlike NATs, live-aboards appear to be an unknown and neglected group in terms of general awareness and social policy. Simultaneously we will examine the issues surrounding the question of whether live-aboard lifestyle is a choice or a consequence of socioeconomic hardship by exploring Bauman's (1998) concepts tourists and vagabonds. It is further proposed that a sense of community among the respondents is strong and they do not generally adhere to consumerist values.

Based on the above concept a qualitative investigation, based on Bristol and Bath set to test this question. The interviews are supplemented with a method of participant observation. The results of my study, based on 14 interviews and some supportive field notes indicate that the experiences of live-aboards resemble those of New Age Travellers. Live-aboards are subject to prejudices and discrimination which is made worse by the increasing legislation of waterways. Due to their socioeconomic circumstances their experiences are closer to the experiences of vagabonds than that of tourists. Additionally, rejection of consumerist values characterises their lives in the waterways community.

Indeed, live-aboards live in a community which combines a sense of freedom with security. My discussion will underline the responsibility of authorities to increase our awareness of live-aboards. Because communities provide important social networks and act as watchdogs for canal and river areas their action should be supported.

Literature Review

The Inland Waterways

Based on my observations and discussions and review of local and national policy it is apparent that, unlike NATs live-aboards are an unknown and neglected in terms of social policy and general awareness. UK's inland waterways are managed by approximately 30 navigation authorities. Each has its own legislation governing the operation of its waterways (ODPM, 2005). On the whole the overall responsibility for inland waterways in Britain belongs to central government. A report by the Inland Waterways Amenity Advisory Council (IWAA) (1996) points out the failure of government to produce an integrated statement of government policy for the waterways system. At least eight government departments share the responsibility. The Department of the Environment (DoE), the sponsor of British Waterways (BW), has an overall responsibility for waterway regulation, but not even them has a comprehensive remit for today's waterways. BW plans its managing of this complex network together with DoE but their documents are not published. BW's objectives, agreed with government, are to run its affairs on commercial basis and to comply with financial targets. BW gets its income from leisure businesses, leisure uses, and property management and development. IWAA remarks that these income sources fall far short of need. Among the smaller organizations there is even bigger diversity, which derive their funding from equally diverse sources (e.g. grants, central and local government). IWAA criticizes the whole waterway scene, arguing that it is riddled with anomalies. Indeed, while some waterways receive funding, others do not. More fundamentally, the ownership in some cases is unclear. IWAA gives a grim picture of today's waterways and concludes that there is an absence of forward-looking national policy. Lee and McDowall (2003) assert that it does not take much effort to see why BW policy tends to discourage on-line moorings on the canals, preferring off-line moorings in basins or in marinas. This way BW can financially benefit more from live-aboards.

Rising House Prices and Shortage of Moorings

The main reason provided for the number of people living on boats in the UK is due to the dramatic reduction in the availability of affordable housing, which puts pressure especially on young people wanting to own their own home (Hutson and Liddiard, 1994; Bath and North East Somerset Local Plan, 2002). A study by the Royal Institution of Chartered Surveyors (2003) suggests that the shortage of affordable housing is creating an 'underclass' of people who cannot afford their own home (BBC, 2003).

In addition, besides the monopoly of BW over the moorings and licensing regulations, there is a considerable shortage of permanent residential moorings along the River Avon and the Kennet and Avon Canal (Bath & North East Somerset Council, 2002). Bath & North East Somerset Council acknowledges that residential moorings can play a useful role in helping to meet the housing requirements of the District, including the need for affordable homes. They suggest that residential moorings should be subject to the same considerations in terms of impact on the character and appearance of the landscape as other forms of residential development (Para

B7.121). Also Hiley (1973) criticizes a shortage of moorings caused by the increasing demand for land for development. She remarks that moorings have become virtually unobtainable. Any evicted live-aboard would face difficulties in finding an alternative mooring. Moreover, the value of their houseboat "would be reduced often below the level of hire-purchase balance, resulting in the loss of family's life savings as well as their home" (Hiley, 1973:23). More than thirty years later Department for Communities and Local Government (2006) compiled a summary of responses to the consultation paper on security of tenure. It shows that most live-aboards were worried about the monopoly of BW over the moorings and the waterways. The respondents also expressed feelings of powerlessness to act to large increases in rent.

The previously mentioned literature reviews the political context in which live-aboards have evolved. Availability of affordable housing is a matter of concern for those wanting to own their own home. Similarly, shortage of residential moorings causes concern in many. Finally, those living aboard are subject to the monopoly of BW over the moorings and waterways as a whole.

Live-aboards as New Age Travellers?

Both a considerable body of literature and a respectable amount of research have emerged over the past years examining New Age Travellers (Martin, 2002; McKay, 1996; Hetherington, 2000). New Age Travellers, who emerged from the hippie movement in the 1960s travel across the country in cars, vans, old coaches, decommissioned ambulances, double decked buses and caravans. They are often resented by conventional members of society because they occupy land and open spaces for musical gatherings. Martin and Hetherington disagree about the nature of NATs. Martin criticizes Hetherington's account of NATs as postmodern Travellers, whose lifestyles are romantic and tranquil. Martin's proposes an approach that takes into account the experiences of those who are forced to travel due to their socioeconomic circumstances. He links the experiences of NATs to Bauman's vagabonds as opposed to Hetherington's portrayal of NATs which resembles the experience of the tourist. This debate above exemplifies how the different portrayals of NATs emphasize different aspects in their lives. The advocates who tend to romanticize New Age Travelling may ignore the fact that some Travellers may be forced on the road because they have previously experienced social and economic difficulties.

Media representation of Travellers suggests that this group routinely display certain negative characteristics not only typical but essential to the group. Media often perceives NATs as being synonymous with the marginal and deviant (Morris, 2000). In order to define something that is not clear, many engage in simplifications and follow the thinking of the media.

Travellers...live on the fringe of society, shun convention and often disregard the rights of others...It's just that the Travellers' culture and behaviour is almost incompatible with the way most of us live

(Bristol Evening Post editorial 29.9.1998 in Beacon Council)

Some Travellers explain that people are envious and jealous of their lifestyle and that is why they turn these feelings into hatred (Traveller quoted in Lowe and Shaw, 1993:239). The respondents of this study expressed similar opinions: "Lot of people say: I really envy you. That is just because they're not brave enough to try" (Rose, 45).

In similar vein, Hiley (1973) criticizes the way boat dwellers are constructed as 'the Other'

- just because they live on a boat instead of a house. She wants to remind that most live-aboards take considerable pride in looking after their homes, contributing to the visual side of the waterside environment. Confirming Hiley's point, live-aboards can act as 'watch dogs', helping to deter vandals and protect riverside property at no cost to the community.

We [live-aboards] still suffer from the impression given to the public by a minority of miscreants who live on boats. Somehow a few hippies smoking pot on one boat in one place manage to give all live-aboards a bad name. If they lived in a flat they would not give all flat-dwellers a bad image. It must be that people are prejudiced against us because they see us as different (Hiley, 1973:22)

Many sociologists recognize the difficulties in defining NATs and argue that they are the most disunited and ill-defined people (Acton, 1974; Clark, 1997). Earle et al (1994) define NATs as people of settled background who adopted a travelling lifestyle in the more recent past, although some are in their third or fourth generation of travelling. Similarly, live-aboards can be perceived as people with no history of travelling. Furthermore, my observations of live-aboards find echo in Clark's (1997:129) account of NATs as being from middle class backgrounds, degree-educated, 'alternative' and anti-materialist.

Unlike Gypsies and Irish Travellers, NATs and live-aboards are not recognized as distinct ethnic groups under the Race Relations Act. However, planning law applies a non-ethnic definition of 'Gypsy' to all Travellers including live-aboards. This definition emphasizes lifestyle as oppose to race. Gypsies according to this definition are defined as "persons of nomadic habit of life, whatever their race or origin, other than group of travelling showmen, travelling together as such" (McKay 1996:48).

These definitions prove useful in our exploration of the lifestyles of the respondents of this study. Some of the respondents have lived in buses and caravans before moving on a boat. Conversely, other respondents of this study have no history of travelling and their boat represented the first mobile home for them. Therefore, the participants of this study include current live-aboards / to be live-aboards / ex- live-aboards. The participants either live, will live or have lived *permanently* on their boats s/he owns or co-owns. Those who hire boats or use their boat only for holiday purposes are not regarded as live-aboards. A boat is defined as any boat that can be used for residential purposes. This definition includes for example a traditional narrow boat, wide beam boat, motor cruiser and a sailing boat.

In summary, the discussion above explores the definitional issues concerning New Age Travellers and live-aboards. Media representations of Travellers are often biased and demonstrate an attempt to present Travellers in a stereotypical fashion. Both NATs and live-aboards are cultural groups but due to their heterogenous nature they are difficult to pin down. The following section discusses the way that the government confronts Travellers.

Managing Travelling on Land and Water

NATs are said to live on benefits and to lead a deviant, immoral lifestyle. The construction of this particular group as deviant and dangerous (Cohen, 1980) helps to promote legislation to control the group, promoting a modern Foucauldian surveillance society. To use Foucault's (1977) arguments, people are being observed and controlled by the invisible machinery of disciplinary power. What is more, the discourse adopted by politicians i.e. labelling of Travellers, seems to be a popular political tool. Labour home secretary Jack Straw, for example,

claimed that there was "too much tolerance of Travellers" (cited from Lodge, 2003). Margaret Thatcher argued that Travellers are not willing to participate fully in society. In an attempt to weed out non-conformity, The Criminal Justice Public Order Act 1994 (CJA) legislation set to criminalize Travelling making life harder for Britain's Travellers. The government repealed their duty to provide sites for Travellers and withdrew grant aid for sites. This forced many Gypsies and Travellers onto unsuitable stopping places or into conventional housing unsuited to their cultural needs.

The CJA has been widely interpreted as signalling the beginning of the end of a viable nomadic existence in Britain, as well as representing a further entrenchment of the powers of the state at the expense of civil liberties. In relation to Travellers the CJA withdrew the former duty to provide adequate sites for Gypsies whilst simultaneously rendering unauthorized sites liable to preemptory evictions, and Travellers themselves faced the prospect of criminalization for following a nomadic lifestyle
(Murdoch, 1998:i).

Following this, the government encouraged Gypsies and Travellers to set their own sites. At the same time planning permissions, which are applicable to live-aboards as well, became harder to obtain (McKay, 1996). Beacon Council (2006) remarks that only ten per cent of Gypsies and Travellers initial planning applications got accepted as compared to eighty per cent of applications of settled population. In addition, 25 per cent of those living in caravans in Britain are homeless because they have nowhere legal to park and face frequent evictions.

In this vein, as McKay remarks, New Age Travelling can be perceived as a product of shifting socioeconomic circumstances and increasing legislation in Britain. On the other hand, as Hetherington and Martin point out, Travellers fulfil a function. Travellers oppose the norms of the society while at the same time they strengthen the normative order of society. Confirming Staines's (1995 cited in McKay) point of view it appears that difficulties Travellers already face in accessing the law is made worse by the legislation used by police, councils and landowners against them.

The discussion above examines the attempts to promote a modern Foucauldian surveillance society. The criminalization of travelling and policy of denial of sites seems like an extreme example of this. The discourse adopted by politicians further reinforces the labelling of Travellers. It can be argued that the need to manage travelling on land has led to attempts to manage travelling on water.

The ongoing debate about the rights and obligations of the Continuous Cruisers illustrates BW's attempt to manage travelling on water. 'Continuous Cruiser' is defined as a person who lives afloat and cruises extensively without the need for permanent mooring (Lee and McDowall 2003:14). The heart of the debate concerns overstaying at public moorings which applies to all boaters, not just live-aboards. Mooring Guidance for Continuous Cruisers "Seeks to explain...the nature of the compulsory movement that must take place (BW, 2004:1)". Unless a shorter time (24hr or 48hr or 72hr) is specified, Continuous Cruisers cannot stay in one place for more than fourteen days. However, BW has not clarified how far one should move and what is the definition of 'place'. Residential Boat Owners Association (RBOA) argues that boaters who abuse the system by over-staying in one place, give live-aboards as a whole a bad name. In its publication it labels the owners of *untidy* boats as those who abuse the system.

Such abuse of the system is unfortunately frequently associated with an untidy

appearance of the boats and their surroundings. Without penalising those who use the system fairly RBOA is working together with BW to improve the situation (2003:16).

Based on my observations and informal discussions with people, the current image of live-aboards as 'crusties' or 'druggies' is the image many have. Indeed, continuous cruising is the cheapest option to live afloat. Depending on the length of one's boat, licenses cost £ 400 - £ 500 per year. Additionally, live-aboard lifestyle is the most independent lifestyle one can legally have. Personal liability for Council Tax, for example, depends on one's rights over the mooring. While these rules are not applied consistently, those in specific dedicated mooring are normally required to pay Council Tax at Band A. Continuous Cruisers therefore are not liable for Council Tax (Lee and McDowall, 2003).

To summarize, travelling on water is becoming increasingly restricted. BW aims to manage travelling on water by imposing rules where and for how long one is allowed to moor. These rules are targeted especially towards Continuous Cruisers, who are required to move to another location after a certain time limit. The following chapter reviews Bauman's (1998) tourists and vagabonds in relation to live-aboards.

Tourists or Vagabonds?

Bauman (1998) describes the class differences between people by using metaphors of 'tourist' and 'vagabond'. He links the class differences between people to their degree of mobility. The experiences that originate from their degree of mobility characterize those high and those low in the hierarchy. Tourists can travel whenever they want and wherever they want. They can also come back to where they left. Vagabonds get kicked out from the site they would rather stay in. Bauman links the lives of the bottom and the top of the society to space and time:

The shrinking of space abolishes the flow of time. The inhabitants of the first world live in a perpetual present, going through a succession of episodes hygienically insulated from their past as well as their future. These people are constantly busy and perpetually 'short of time'...People marooned in the opposite world are crushed under the burden of abundant, redundant, and useless time they have nothing to fill with. In their time 'nothing ever happens'...They can only kill time, as they are slowly killed by it. Residents of the first world live in time; space does not matter for them, since spanning any distance is instantaneous. Resident of the second world, on the contrary live in space: heavy, resilient, untouchable, which ties down time and keeps it beyond residents' control
(Bauman 1998:88)

Bauman's notion of tourists in relation to live-aboards is not very convincing. He argues for the shrinking of space with the help of fast means of transportation (or for example World Wide Web). However, speed of travelling is determined by one's boat and in any case is far from instantaneous. For that reason, the flow of time cannot be abolished either. For any live-aboard the flow of time is present - 'all the time'.

Shrinking of space has occurred but on a more concrete level than Bauman proposed. The actual space for cruising has been shrinking because of the increased regulation of waterways. Live-aboards can no longer stop in a beautiful place for as long as they want. Additionally, with the current house prices it is virtually impossible for any young person to buy a property in England. People seek for alternative ways of owning their homes. For these reasons it is hardly a

surprise that some parts of the canals get overcrowded. There might be freedom to travel whenever you want but not *wherever you want*. There are two reasons for this. Some canals and rivers are still derelict. Money and volunteer labour is needed to build the waterway system up (Lee and McDowall, 2003). Another reason is lack of sites for stopping, which can be seen as an unfortunate side effect of the power of the capitalist to exploit the land (and people living on that land) for the purpose of making profit. The space that used to belong to the public is now controlled by authority. For Bauman this is a spatial consequence for globalization: loss of public space to privately controlled spaces.

Bauman's notion of vagabonds is more promising, especially in relation to live-aboards who want to live as cheap as possible. First, there are these 'economic live-aboards'. Then there are those whose boats are out of water. Being deprived for years of what boating is about, being on water, they have lot of time on their disposal. The researcher defines them as 'an underclass of the boating world'. I liken these both groups to vagabonds. Indeed, their consumption power is limited. Interestingly, as Bauman notes, the current political obsession with law and order and the criminalization of poverty is an attempt to bring a vagabond-free society around. However, a vagabond free society is not the only utopia Bauman talks about. Community, he asserts, is another 'paradise lost'. The researcher, however, is not convinced.

Our discussion above offers one possible way to perceive Travellers. The researcher, however, emphasizes the socioeconomic hardship faced by the respondents and suggest that it is the main reason for living aboard. The following section introduces the role of community that appears to be important for the respondents of this study.

Community

As mentioned before for Bauman (2001) community stands for another 'paradise lost' : it can only exist in our imagination. In addition, the price one pays for community is freedom: "Missing community means missing security; gaining community, if it happens, would soon mean missing freedom" (2001:4). Based on my field observations it seems that community occupies a central role in the lives of the respondents. It also seems to be possible to gain community without losing one's freedom. Bauman rightly asserts that we find safety in sameness and with the help of others we can confront our everyday problems. Agreeing with Bauman, gaining control over our lives in a globalizing world can only take place collectively.

Giddens writes about community on a more concrete level than Bauman. For Giddens the civic decline in contemporary societies is evident "in the weakening sense of solidarity in local communities and urban neighborhoods, high levels of crime, and the break-up of marriages and families (1998:78)". This civic decline, he remarks, is not reducible to economic deprivation nor it is the fault of the welfare state. Indeed, it is governments duty to encourage the renewal of civic culture. Giddens argues for society where communities work together with governments and other institutions to further the social and material refurbishment of neighborhoods. Similarly, live-aboards and volunteers that work together with authorities and institutions can help to improve the visual side of the canals.

In addition, "Communities provide bonds of affection that turn groups of people into social entities resembling extended families" (Etzioni, 2000:15). Especially, those individuals who do not have close ties with their families can benefit from communities. Communities in this sense

can alleviate the traditional role of family. And for some it can be their only family. In similar vein, Etzioni defends communities' role in providing preventive and acute care while they transmit and reformulate a shared moral culture. He argues that, "in communities people help each other rather than merely helping those in need" (2000:19). To illustrate his argument Etzioni stresses the importance of community volunteers schemes, for example 'Neighborhood Watch scheme', which have proven successful in reducing crime. Agreeing with Etzioni, all this helps to reduce the burden of the welfare state.

The previous section explored the role of community in the live-aboard lifestyle. Communities can help the burden of the welfare state, in both individual and societal level. The following section introduces the concept of consumption. While many argue that contemporary societies are characterised by the incitement to consume, there are those who do not consider consumerist values important to life.

Debates on Consumption

Our exploration of the live-aboard lifestyle finds echo in what Foss and Larking (1976 cited in McKay) define as 'post-movement groups'. These post-movement find meaning in escaping the complexities and incongruities of the material reality. Cohen and Taylor (1992) add that many want to escape the normalizing attempts of modern society. World might be viewed as a repressive place and therefore we want to escape order and control. Looking from this angle, live-aboard lifestyle represents one way of escaping. Indeed, being mobile might provide a form of rebellion and criticism against the repression of everyday routines and rituals. Cohen and Taylor assert that this 'fantasy of escaping' is powerfully marketed by the capitalist society and therefore reduced to a level of market. The researcher would like to remark that the previous literature focuses on utopias and fantasies. Yet, we explore something that is very concrete - people who live on their boats. Arguably, live-aboards manage to escape without praising the consumerist values of the capitalist societies.

Similarly, Habermas (1984) argues that the world of work or 'system-world' begins to take over the world of interactions, communicative action and emotions - 'life-world'. Therefore, escaping these suffocating tendencies of modern societies and affirming our affectional and communicative ties may bring us relief. Indeed in live-aboard community these ties can be established and maintained. Finally, Baudrillard's (1998) account of consumption views it as the 'ultimate evil' which defines our identities and relationships. As a consequence spontaneous symbolic human relations cease to exist. His simplistic, totalitarian and gloomy portrayal of the state of modern societies is far from the community spirit that exist amongst live-aboards. Moreover, consumption appear not to constrain the lives of live-aboards.

In summary, the discussion above explores the debate about the importance of consumption in peoples' lives. The researcher argues that consumption does not define the lives and selves of live-aboards. To conclude, the aim of the literature review was to provide the intellectual and factual background for the research and to inform the methodology. These themes discussed here are taken further in the following sections.

Methodology

Research Design

Rejecting the positivist tradition within social science my methodological approach falls under 'interpretative sociology'. Opposing the external truths about the social world, and the methods of natural sciences the researcher adopted a methodological approach which is qualitative. The method of verstehen by Max Weber informed my research. My aim was to interpret the meanings, motives and intentions behind the action of my research subjects by trying to see the world through their eyes. The qualitative data and evidence of my research results from interviews and observations and of analysis of that data. However, as Weber points out, it does not mean that my research provides 'a causally valid explanation, but merely constituting a plausible hypothesis' (Davidson and Layder, 1994: 32).

The research process started with the use of theories discussed in the literature review section. The main method of data gathering was qualitative interviewing. The strength of qualitative interviewing is the opportunity it provides to collect rigorously examined narrative accounts of the social world (Miller and Glassner, 2004 cited in Silverman). This way it was possible to gather in depth information and gain valuable insights based on the wisdom of key respondents (Denscombe, 1998). Above all, the involvement of live-aboards in the project is essential, as they know what life on a boat is like, what are the difficulties they confront in their everyday life and why do they prefer it as opposed to more conventional forms of living. An additional questionnaire at the end of the interview asked basic questions about interviewees' gender, age, occupation, income range, marital status and number of children. The rationale behind the questionnaire stemmed from the aim to get basic demographic facts in time-saving way. Interviews were complemented with a method of participant observation. The observations and experiences of the researcher who has been a live-aboard since May 2006 were an invaluable addition to data from the interviews, adding to the validity of the research. This research does not claim to be 'value free' or 'objective' in the way conventional sociology has encouraged as a methodological ideal (Phillips, 1973). Thus, the study of this reality is not carried out by experts from outside but by the objects of that reality. Hopefully as a result of this ongoing process, the researcher is able to make an original contribution to the body of knowledge of live-aboards. Nevertheless, reliability and validity of the research requires attention. "A study can be said reliable if similar results would be obtained by others using the same questions and the same sample criteria" (Simmons, 2001:90). In a similar vein, a research is said to be valid if it measures what it sets out to measure. Therefore the questions of this research were designed to be clear and unambiguous. As the validity was seen as more to do with the bias that the researcher might have concerning its results the researcher was ready to falsify the hypotheses made before the interviews and approached the study with critical and open mind.

To summarize, combining the material from the interviews with some participant observation intended to make the research more sound. By acknowledging the previous work my hypotheses and choice of research methods got support from other authors (Gilbert 2001:25).

The Sample

The sample used in the research was live-aboards in Bristol and Bath area. The sampling

method was purposive. Arber (2001:61) remarks that purposive samples are good when developing interview schedules and other research instruments. They are useful for exploration and theory development. Interviewees were drawn from a cross-section of a population: all genders, different age ranges and different employment statuses. Pilot work was conducted on three participants to test the interview questions. The researcher assessed the representativeness of the achieved sample and identified the nature of any bias (Moser and Kalton 1971 cited in Gilbert 2001:75). Telephone follow-ups were done when some particular interview response needed clarification. One interviewee was contacted again because it was felt that his situation might be changing (and it was). However, this sample does not claim to be representative of the live-aboards from which it was selected.

14 live-aboards were interviewed, four of them women. Their age ranged from 25 to 74 years. All interviewees, except for one, were British. One interviewee had gone through a gender exchange. At the time of the interview eight participants have not ever been married, three of them were divorced and three of them were married. Those who have never been married, two were in a relationship the time that was interviewed. Of those who were divorced, one had a relationship the time that was interviewed. All participants reported educational achievements and occupational history. At the time of the interview two were unemployed, one worked part-time, one was a full time mum, one was a student and one was retired after losing his job. All others worked full time. At the time of the interview two participants were no longer boat-dwellers. In addition one couple was waiting for their boat to finish while they rented a flat. All others lived permanently on their boats. Eight participants earned less than £10,000 a year, two participants earned £10,000 - 15,000, and four participants earned more than £20,000 a year (three of them women). Three of the participants were continuous cruisers, four had a permanent mooring and four lived on their boats on dry land. One lived on an unauthorised site. All current boat-dwellers of this study, except for one, will continue their boat-dwelling. Those currently not living on a boat were considering it again as a possible form of living.

Access to Sources

The policy experts were reluctant to provide information. Several institutions were approached in an attempt to acquire basic information concerning the daily lives of live-aboards. Amongst others Planning Policy Office in Bath and Tax Office in Bristol did not respond to my enquiries about live-aboards' liability to council tax. After buying RBOA's booklet "Living Afloat" the researcher was provided with information other institutions were inapt to provide. What is more, the researcher was refused interviews by Bristol Marina - albeit a private marina and not obliged to inform me of their policies - and by the Harbour Master on several occasions.

To conclude, my main research method, semi-structured interviewing was complemented with participant observation which involved informal conversations with people and observation of daily lives of live-aboards. Especially, data from the interviews was tested against my experiences inside the community. These methods were supported with relevant literature, which will provide the social, historical and political background necessary for understanding the context in which today's live-aboards have evolved.

Self Reflection on Methods

Agreeing with Bernard (2006:212) semi-structured interviewing is best in situations where interviewer only gets one chance to interview someone. The researcher followed a general interview guide (Appendix I), which covered a list of topics. that was followed by a short questionnaire (Appendix II) The interview guide provided flexibility that was needed to follow new leads while producing comparable and reliable qualitative data. This made the researcher feel prepared and being in control of the interview situation. The interviews aimed to find out about individual histories, lifestyle choices and personal experiences of the interviewees. The interviewees were also asked how do they think other people perceive them. Questions were compiled in a clear and unambiguous way. In order to maintain objectivity, leading questions were avoided. The use of a tape recorder gave the researcher a change to concentrate on the actual interview. Focusing on the interviewee, engaging in eye-contact and non-verbal communication generally made the respondents feel at ease.

Interviewing may be affected by class-based assumptions. My experience was that participants, whatever their class background, were happy to tell their stories. Even though some of them had low socio-economic status, all were highly intelligent and often university educated. Only once when a participant was tight-lipped in his responses it was felt that my 'foreign background' pervaded the interviewing relationship. However, it was *not* felt that this particular interviewee was trying to give socially acceptable answers (Labov, 1972; Patton, 1989 cited in Seidman, 1991:80).

Ethical Considerations

Reflecting back on the power issues present in this particular research, there was mutual respect between the researcher and the participants. Hence the participants were treated as legitimate authors and it was felt that the research was conducted ethically (Bulmer & Warwick, 1983). The research was based on informed consent "which refers to a freely given agreement on the part of the researched to become a subject of the research process" (May 2001:60). The aim of the research was fully explained to the research participants. Protecting the identities of the respondents occupies a central position in social research. Following the 'Code of Ethical Practice' the respondents understood that they are afforded anonymity and confidentiality and that they are able to reject the use of tape-recorders (British Sociological Association cited in Gilbert, 2001). Data is presented in such a way that respondents should be able to recognize themselves, while the reader should not be able to identify them (Barnes 1979: 39). According to the Data Protection Act (1998) which came into effect in 2000, violation of anonymity and privacy can have legal implications. Therefore the participants were made aware of their right to know the type of information that is held of them and that they can obtain a copy of this project. The researcher followed what Bulmer (1982: 255 in Denzin and Lincoln 1994: 92) wrote about confidentiality: "Identities, locations of individuals and places are concealed in published results, data collected are held in anonymised form and all data kept securely confidential". The participants were assured that information given to her will be used for research purposes only and not handed to any third party. Additionally, respondents' real names were not used. Personal information was held under secure conditions and destroyed by the end of the research. Interviews were transcribed as soon as possible and the interview files were deleted after

transcription.

Discussion

People live on boats for variety of reasons. Some like being close to water and nature.

Some dislike house-dwelling. Some have faced socioeconomic difficulties (break-up of a marriage/ unemployment) that have led to their lifestyle. **(OFFAmongst the participants)** the most frequently mentioned motives to live aboard were the financial reasons. Besides being cheaper than renting an apartment or a house, live-aboard lifestyle also offered a sense of freedom. For many, as for Diane (35, boat-fitter/mother, live-aboard for 9 years) live-aboard lifestyle is a combination of things: *"It's mixture of freedom and security...Everyone seems to be rather like me"*.

From House to Boat CHANGE

As discussed in the literature review just because live-aboards live on a boat instead of a house is enough for sedentary society to perceive them in a stereotypical way. It is worth emphasizing that all participants of this study have lived in houses/apartments before they moved aboard. What is more, four participants sold their houses they owned/co-owned in order to move aboard. They were looking for a complete change of lifestyle.

Emily (52, accountant) and John (49, teacher) sold their house in November 2005. Their boat, which cost £ 110, 000 is being built for them, according to their design. Until the boat is ready in December, they rent a flat. They wanted to do something different for couple of years, before their retirement. Emily compared the reasons behind house- and boat-dwelling and said that they are different. Whereas being a live-aboard is a lifestyle choice, house-dwelling is dictated by the location of one's work or family or the overall area.

You choose your house because it's near your work or family or it's an area you want to live in. If you're going to live on a boat you're living with other people who have also chosen that lifestyle as opposed to people who like Tesco's.

As opposed to Emily and John, Andrew (34, musician, part-time shop assistant) bought his boat second-hand in June 2006. Costing a mere £ 30,000 he moved straight in and does the required maintenance work himself. He sold his house partly because he felt unwelcome in his neighborhood and partly due to his divorce. His neighbor harassed him and his non-English lodgers for years. It gradually got worse, leading to Andrew's physical assault.

Our neighbor for six years made me realize that I never want to be stuck in a traditional terraced house. He complained about non-English people walking in and out and about the 'noise'. He got really paranoid about us...He repeatedly broke our windows and threw [dog] shit in [pause]. One day I was mugged unconscious on my own street [pause]. It's a busy street yet none of the neighbors came forward to the police. He thought of me as a Jew and [carved] a star of David on the front door.

As mentioned in the literature review Bath and North Somerset Council acknowledged the shortage of permanent residential moorings in 2002. Considering the shortage of moorings, Emily and John considered themselves lucky for getting a permanent mooring. What added to their living costs was a monthly payment of £ 350 to their future marina to keep the mooring. Judy said: *"At least we got a home"*. On the other hand, Andrew was a Continuous Cruiser. Like others who intended to live on lower budget Andrew made adjustments and compromises on his lifestyle. Yet he did not manage to live much cheaper on his boat than in his house. Since he

bought the boat he had already invested £5,000 on repair and maintenance work.

For Rose (45, teacher, mother) living in a house was a mere status symbol [saying] "*Look how well I'm doing*". Her boat is a place where she can feel happy. Rose and her daughter Anna, have recently moved on a boat again, after 13 years. She co-owned a house with her ex partner. After her relationship ended she invested her share from the house on to a boat. Rose's and Anna's first period of boat-dwelling ended when Anna started school and Rose was contacted by social services. Pressure from the local authorities made them to move back on to a house.

My first period of living on a boat ended when my daughter who is now 17 started school. There was an outrage at school whether Anna is living in a suitable environment. Our case was investigated by social services. Anna was taken to hospital to have the general health check done. It was a lot of pressure and I felt that we need to move back on to a house...People are quick to make judgements. There is a stigma attached to anybody who is seen as participating in a less than standardized lifestyle [especially] when you got kids.

Other participants rented a flat or lived on other mobile homes before they became live-aboards. However, they all agreed that renting is expensive. Justin (25, student, live-aboard for 1 year) lived on his boat on an unauthorized site. He wanted to buy a boat anyway and the only way he could afford it was to live on it. He, amongst other participants said that with these house prices he cannot afford to buy a house. Harry's (41, unemployed) live-aboard experience in the North Sea lasted for three years. It came with a job. He was a pirate radio dj seventeen years ago. Now he considered moving on a boat again, this time in Bristol or Bath. However, if he did not get a permanent mooring it would not be an option: "*Continuous Cruising would not appeal to me very much [because] you'd be chased around*".

CHANGE TO With or Without a Mooring

In addition to Emily, John and Rose, Lucy (38, studio-owner, live-aboard for 4 years) is permanently moored. Along with the other participants, access to work was the main reason for them to have a permanent mooring. Yet, Peter (33, manager, musician, live-aboard for 4 years) who also worked full-time gave up his mooring in the marina.

[We paid] three four grand a year, which was a waste of money as compared to facilities they provide you with. We only chose it because they had space and they let us pay monthly.

Similarly, Diane who lives with her family on a lifeboat, is a Continuous Cruiser. She gave her permanent mooring up few years ago because she felt unwelcome in the area.

I had one really negative screaming shouting argument with a local man who made it clear that I had no right to be there [emotional tone in her voice]. I was heavily pregnant and it just affected me. [He said] that the whole place was alright before I came along. So I thought "I'm just gonna move up and down and keep free head about it all".

The Last Half Per Cent

In order to understand the life-experiences of the participants the researcher paid attention to not only where the participants lived but *how* they lived. The location of where the participants lived had an impact on their life-experiences. So far we have discussed those live-aboards who

have a permanent residential mooring and those live-aboards who have a continuous cruising license. And yet, a group of four set itself apart from the ten other participants by living aboard on dry land. They were deprived of what boating is about - being on water.

Their life-experiences indicated that living aboard, can at times, be challenging. For the purpose of this particular study, and some may disagree, the researcher defined them as an 'underclass' of the boating community. However, as the aim was not to categorize people and further facilitate their labelling, it is up to the reader to decide whether this conceptualization facilitates her/his understanding of this particular group. The criteria used by the researcher was based on their life-experiences that are marked by a constant struggle. Originally, they came on the dry docks to repair their boats. Data from the interviews and observations indicated that beside repairing their boats, other more valid reasons emerged that kept them there. The most obvious reason appeared to be the cheapness of their accommodation. The participants paid £ 20 per boat meter per month which included the use of basic facilities, like public toilets.

Matt (74) has lived on his boat, which has never been on water, for the last six years. His boat had a roof and walls, but no bottom. Besides, his boat was small - Matt was barely able to crawl in to his boat and sit on the floor. However, Matt was not concerned about the actual layout of his boat but rather the friction between him and the owner.

It's all quite stressful down here really. If the boss wanted, he who could give me my marching orders. So I have to live with that.

Ed (48) has been a live-aboard for nearly half of his life. On the dry docks he has lived for the last six years. His boat needed welding. Because of his physical disability it is something he is unable to do.

I was not born on a boat [but] it is nearly twenty years. This is my first boat. The bottom's falling off. I will have to do some more work. Welding.

Keith (42, live-aboard for 1 year) was distressed because he did not know how to repair the engine of his 1944 motor cruiser. He regretted of buying his boat without seeing it. Since his life-savings lie on the boat, it is unlikely that he will get the engine repaired in the near future.

I bought the boat without seeing it. It's a car engine. Once a week I try to fix the engine but it just depresses me because I don't know what I'm doing.

Robert (53, live-aboard for 6 years) said that they all came on the dry docks to repair their boats. Then they stayed. According to Robert live-aboard lifestyle attracts strange characters. He made a comparison between them and the rest of the society by using (**OFFan example of**) 'probability curve' as an example. The 'normal people' live in the middle of this probability curve, whereas the 'last half per cent' lives on the edges. To make it work, the former needs the latter. Based on my observation and interviews with the four participants, they are strange in many ways, but as Robert concludes, pleasant.

The bulk of people - a house, a car, two children and a dog - live in the middle of this probability curve. To make it work, right down on the edges, is the last half percent [lowers his voice as about to tell a secret]. Most of the people are fairly bizarre and unusual. All sorts of people from the unemployable to IT guys, nurses, stone

masons and carpenters. It's a magnet for strange characters. But not nasty ones. Most of the people are very pleasant. Everybody's different. The last half percent.

Matt shared his story of how he became a live-aboard. He built his boat while he lived in a goat shed with his dog. Matt tried to stay positive but it was evident that he was distressed.

I've been sort of land locked for the last six years actually. I lost my job at the age of 59. My wife left me, she had no future with me. I couldn't afford to live in a flat. It cost to heat. I did get housing benefit but that went on to fags. This [boat] was made in my niece's garden. I stayed in their old goat shed for 18 months. [It's] a sort of Ikea flat pack. I arrived here with my dog on Christmas Eve. We put this cabin up first. After couple of days I got flooded. After that my son came down and we built it all together. Then life took off from there.

None of these four participants had showers or toilets on their boats. Keith and Matt also lacked cooking facilities. Keith said he can survive without cooking facilities.

Ed: you must get some gas. You must get some proper cooking facilities.

Keith: I went to Army. I can handle things like that.

Ed: You must be tougher than me then. You must be.

Living in these conditions can be stressful for anyone. The life-experiences of these participants were marked by struggle. Yet they had no need to gloss over their experiences. Matt illustrated his life-experiences with the extract of 'sanitation business'. After his description he said he would not mind living in a house.

Another thing here, is sanitation business. You fetch your water from the tap. Then the waste goes into a container and you march it up to the Elsan thing at night with the spray all over. Then it goes into the main drain. It must weigh 40 pound. [Pause] So that's life on a boat [Sighs]. My eventual plan is to give it another couple of years. I'd like my own studio flat. It's beautiful around there, [Name of the place]. So you got a tap and a toilet, instead of all this business. I'm 74 next Thursday. And I still, you know, keep going.

After Matt shared this experience he felt that he needs to explain himself to me. He sounded melancholic. Yet, the other participants felt that there is no need to be apologetic or feel ashamed.

Matt: I don't know. There is no cure really.

Robert: No, there isn't any cure and why should there be? There shouldn't be a cure, for God's sake. There's nothing wrong with us. It might be old age.

Matt: Oh yeah, it's harmless nuttiness really.

Robert: We're all off the age, but you know we're not harmful, we don't upset people. We just carry on.

Matt: Living.

Ed: Doing our thing.

Obviously, the consumption power among the above participants was limited. They were

forced to be anti-consumerists. However, they saw the positive side of it. Robert said that almost everything they needed can be found in the skip. Amongst other participants these four participants said that winters can get wet and cold. Robert hoped to find a stove.

People who have their boats repaired throw awful lot of stuff away. Usually whatever you want - a chair, a radio, canvas turns up. You look into skip and there is one...No-one's thrown away a stove yet.

In avoiding to be "crushed under the burden of abundant, redundant, and useless time" these participants "killed" time with various hobbies. Mat's hobby crafts consisted of colorful costumes, hats and a parrot made of felt. Next to his boat stood a wooden racer which was painted bright yellow and decorated with pictures of his dog, which had passed away. He talked about people who live on their boats and who seek comfort in alcohol. Matt, however, considered hobby making a better option.

The trouble is, with particularly men past their retirement. They are lost and they need something to do. They either take up golf or some hobby. Lots of take up the booze. This is totally mad [points at his handicraft]. It kept me occupied. It's a bit of therapy really.

Towards the end of the interview Robert returned to the same theme the interview began with. It felt like a good moment to finish the interview with them.

Robert: *We are the last half percent.*

Ed: *You're not very complementary are you [laughs].*

Robert: *What? It's great. Can you imagine a community of people like this?*

Keith: *Like us. No.*

Robert: *Unless you live in a caravan in some bloody field with half a dozen other people and loads of dogs.*

Keith: *We all got the same problems.*

Ed: *We all got through.*

CHANGE TO Nomads

Leaving aside the lives of the above participants, the life-experiences of the other participants were less demanding. Richard (37, shop assistant) lives in his refitted ambulance. He used to live on a fishing boat in the 1990s until he sold his boat and went busking in Europe. After he returned from Europe he rented and squatted. He considered living aboard again.

I never feel the urge to settle down in one place. My lifestyle as a live-aboard was very basic indeed - I did live in it the whole time with no heating essentially. I had problems with damp and it was cold. But it was cheaper and less hassle than living in a van. It was still very enjoyable. Having a mobile home gives a feeling of being less tied down and being less oppressed by the world.

Also Richard, Andrew, Diane, Peter and Rose mentioned that they preferred a mobile home. Peter and his wife have a history of travelling. Peter explained that they have always preferred mobile homes and disliked house-dwelling.

[Before moving on to a boat] we've been to buses, caravans, bendovers and

tree houses. Before that we lived about a year and a half in two different houses. We didn't like living in a house. All these empty rooms and the stuff that was boxed up. We just wanted to go back to being a bit more mobile.

Before boat-dwelling, Diane squatted in Bristol, but did not like the drug scene it came with. On the other hand, living in a van lacked security. She lived with her parents for a while whilst working full-time. After that she was able to buy her own boat.

I found renting a constant struggle in Bristol so I ended up squatting there. That was ok but there was too much heroine around. I really wanted to own my own home and space. I wanted more security than the van thing. I wanted to be free to move about because I didn't have fixed idea where I wanted to be. And I still don't.

Peter, Diane and Richard found BW's regulations less hard to comply than land base regulations for travellers. Peter explains:

There is lot of hassle if you wanna travel on waterways. But actually it is a lot less hassle than being in a truck...If you're in a 50 ft truck and pull aside the road you wouldn't last a night. Police would be there within an hour to move you out.

The reluctance of local authorities to provide sites for land base Travellers, together with increased legislation in Britain seemed to make live-aboard lifestyle a good option for Diane, Peter and Richard. Moreover, they mentioned that boat-dwellers enjoyed more respect than land base Travellers. However, they all remarked that the younger generation looks down on them. Peter said:

Some bored teenage lads tend to think you're bunch of pikies - a dirty travelling skum. And we think they're just bunch of peasants living in a house with their tight little square.

Most participants felt that the general public only likes *traditional* narrow boats, which are picturesque and beautiful. Lucy, Peter and Rose live on traditional narrow boats. And yet, as Rose remarked, they faced prejudices:

Sometimes people look at you [and think that] "They must be living in a squalor because there is stuff out on the roof and stuff on the back of the boat. They must be some sort of strange type of traveller hippies. They must be spreading anarchy".

Many participants said that they noticed a change in people's attitudes towards live-aboards which coincided with the increased regulations of the canal system. When Diane began her boat-dwelling she was able to moor wherever she wanted for as long as she wanted. After she received her first sticker which told her to "Move!" she never stayed in one place for more than fourteen days.

Nearly all participants blamed the press coverage for creating a biased picture of live-aboards. Some participants noted that it was unfair that they were accused of littering the canal area. Diane said that they were blamed for the ignorance of the authorities to organize litter picking in the canal area:

There was some really scathing articles in the local press about the filth

and stuff, which is ridiculous. Considering that there is no litter picking whatsoever, it is as clean as anything.

Also Peter and Rose noticed the change in attitudes towards boaters. Peter said that couple of years ago BW together with the press wanted create a picture of live-aboards as "*a bunch of filthy Travellers*". Rose mentioned that it was a moral panic about Travellers: "*a fear about people who don't conform*". Andrew, Justin, Emily and John remarked that the general public may view live-aboards as Gypsies. Emily emphasized that their future marina tries to avoid the 'Gypsy-image'. She said that these kind of people unfortunately exist and that they give boat-dwellers as a whole a bad name.

Our marina won't let you live aboard unless you're working [pause]. They're trying to avoid [looks back and checks if anyone is listening] the Gypsy camp [pause] scenario. There's quite a lot of problems people not paying for their licenses. Your boat doesn't have to be a mess and you don't have to be a mess. And you need to keep the tow path neat. I think it's people like that that give people on boats a bad name. Our boat builder calls them 'Crusty Cruisers' - the drop outs from society.

Many participants felt that property developers and authorities who build expensive apartments want to clean the canals of live-aboards. Ed mentioned: "*Basically they'd like to set you on concrete and build a flat on top of you.*" Richard referred to 1992 when he was a live-aboard and described how BW introduced the new rules:

They made the whole area a 'Continuous Cruising - area' by enforcing the rules. They moved the whole community of people out and made [them] essentially homeless by enforcing the rules.

Some participants noted that when the overall quality and status of the canal area improved it attracted people with money. Those who bought their houses with a lot of money presumed that they were more entitled to be there than live-aboards. Lucy got agitated when talking about it.

You know what really annoys me. People in the posh flats complain about the boats. Live-aboards have been there for years. [Yet] suddenly when they buy the posh flat they think they own the land as well. Robbery I think.

CHANGE: To Consume or not to Consume

(TAKE OFF: After examining how society confronts live-aboards, next we will explore the importance of consumerist values among the participants. Indeed,)most participants mentioned that since they moved on a boat, they tended to consume less. **ADD: Indeed, live-aboards have to organize electricity, water, gas and sewage themselves).** Andrew and Richard wanted to have as little impact on environment as possible and said that they can live with using small amount of water and electricity. Others mentioned that they are more aware of their energy consumption than when they lived in a house/flat. Lucy said:

Obviously you fill a [water] tank on your boat, you're more aware of your consumption when you're brushing you're teeth. Same with my gas supply, I'm not wasteful with it.

However, not every participant was anti-consumerist. Emily and John wanted to have some luxury on their boat:

We wanted this really expensive, £ 5 000 sound system. They are going to fit it for us. We will have speakers in the bedroom, where we can work with the remote control. And water proof speakers outside for the canal parties.

CHANGE TO: Community among Live-aboards

(TAKE OFF: **What is more,**)the participants reported a sense of community amongst them. Most participants said it was nice to belong to a community. Some compared it to living in a village where everyone knows each others doings. Confronting the everyday problems with help of others made life more fun and in some cases 'more bearable'. Rather than constructed as consumers whose dealings with each other are reducible to cold and calculated interactions, the waterways community is characterised by warm interactions and reciprocity. The researcher was offered help several times by the participants. Rose gave me a tour about the available moorings, Harry fixed our alternator and Lucy offered help with the electrics. Ed, Keith, Matt and Robert mentioned that in a live-aboard community they can be social and talk to their neighbours. People they meet are likely to respond in kind. Robert said:

Somehow [live-aboard lifestyle] filteres out people who are violent or serious drug addicts. You're left with this strange group of people who are very sociable.

However, Diane complained that at times there can be too much community. She enjoyed a lack of community when she stayed in her caravan, but after a while it was good to be back.

There is that community thing, which is strong. It can get a bit of overstrained sometimes, but it's got hell of a lot down for it. When I was six months in a caravan to do up this boat, I really enjoyed the lack of community and lack of belonging to some sort of group identity. Now it's really lovely to be back.

The experiences of the researcher find echo in what Etzioni wrote about community's role in preventing crime. During a two week period in Bristol, the researcher witnessed three separate occasions when group of boys broke in to people's boats. Besides break-ins, they damaged one boat so badly that it sank during the night. What is more, police did not have resources to arrive. Being upset about these incidents, the researcher was offered support from the neighboring boat-dwellers. After several weeks of these incidents police finally took initiative to introduce Neighborhood Watch Scheme in the area.

This experience of being unsafe was voiced by the respondents of this study. Diane, Lucy and Rose mentioned that they tend to moor their boats next to others to feel safe. Of the male respondents, Andrew, Justin, Peter and Richard raised concern about the increasing mischief and crime directed towards boats. Considering what Hiley wrote about live-aboards acting as 'watch dogs' and helping to deter vandals at no cost to the community, Peter remarked that live-aboard community saved BW a lot of money:

If anything goes wrong in the canal, when there is a kid torturing a swan, rubbish floating about, a boat lose the first people who gonna do anything about it are the live-aboards. Everytime. It's just sort of a thing you do.

Finally, all other participants, except Andrew, were planning to continue their boat dwelling. Many considered of buying a bigger boat. Those who were not boat-dwelling at the time of the interview considered it as an option. After four months of living on a boat Andrew's boat was for sale.

I expected boat-dwelling to be less hassle. Canal life is as regulated as any. I feel as unfree as I did when I lived in a Bedminster terrace. It's not much cheaper either. Things come with a price. To afford them you have to play along the career game. Or to be dedicated to the 'alternative lifestyle', which I can't be bothered with.

In summary, the results confirmed three things. First, the results showed that the participants considered the picture of the sedentary society of them biased. Many participants were treated badly or perceived stereotypically by the media or general public. Second, many, but not all participants opposed consumerist values. Third, a sense of community amongst live-aboards was strong. Community's role as a watchdog and also, taking care of those with limited socioeconomic resources was remarkable.

Conclusions, Critical Evaluation and Recommendations

The researcher's primary goal was to describe and analyze the daily lives of live-aboards by looking at the socioeconomic circumstances and political context in which live-aboards have evolved. I believe that the method of interviewing combined with field observations was the most useful in our exploration of their lifestyles.

The study findings substantiate my hypotheses that the prejudices and discrimination live-

aboards experience resemble those experienced by New Age Travellers. Indeed general public and media look down on live-aboards. These factors, together with the increased regulations of the waterways make life harder for individual live-aboards. Importantly, my findings indicate that boat-dwelling does not seem to be always a choice, but **(off:ALSO)** a consequence of the socioeconomic hardship. These live-aboards are akin to Bauman's vagabonds.

Despite of the one particular occasion when the participants engaged in wasteful consumption my hypotheses of live-aboard lifestyle as anti-consumerist **WAS SUPPORTED**. Finally, the study findings verify the existence of communal ties between live-aboards. indeed, communities act as a provider of practical advice and social support.

In future more research is required on live-aboards. Because the study sample was small and non representative and the selection process was made purposively, the results of this study are only suggestive. Therefore they cannot be generalized to a wider population. A longitudinal study with a larger sample would be needed to evaluate whether the results of this study are valid and representative.

Despite the limitations of this study, a few recommendations can be made for addressing the general awareness **(off:and social policy)** concerning those individuals who live on boats. In this vein, social policies that concern live-aboards should be made more accessible to all. Only by increasing general awareness about **THE** live-aboard lifestyle can public perceptions of liveaboards as a homogenous group be challenged.

MORE IMPORTANTLY,rather than concentrating on regulating and curbing the phenomena British Waterways together with other smaller authorities, should work closely with boaters **(off:IN GENERAL)**to improve local community standards and civil behaviour. As we saw, communities can help to reduce the burden of the welfare state. First, community programs can reduce the expenses of governments in preventing crime. Second, communities can play a role in reducing isolation amongst **THOSE** whose social contacts outside the community are not satisfying.

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INTERVIEW

1. What are people's first reactions when you tell them that you live on a boat?

2. Have you always lived on a boat? Yes: would you ever consider living in a house?

No: what was the deciding factor?

3. How did you find it in the beginning?

Was it different from what you expected? Were there some things (faults, leaks, regulations) you only later found out?

4. Have you got a permanent mooring? Yes: was it easy to get? Did you get it where you wanted? No: How come? Does it suit your lifestyle? Is it something you prefer?

5. So, tell me how you came to live on a boat in " " ?

Why did you choose " " ?

6. What is it like being moored here? How does " " compare to your previous places?

Is it a friendly community / Do people look out for each other?

7. Why do you think people in general live on boats?

What's the appeal? Would you recommend it?

8. What do you think other people think of people who live on boats?

9. What advice would you give to someone planning to move on a boat?

What have you learned about it?

10. Are you planning to continue living on a boat?

In Bristol, Bath/somewhere else?

11. Have you got any other comments, points you think I've missed?

QUESTIONNAIRE

1. Age :

2. Occupation :

3. Income range (please tick)

Under £ 10,000

£10-15,000

£15 – 20,000

£20,000 or over

4. Gender :

5. (please tick)

Living with partner

Living alone

6. Number of children, if any :

7. Currently moored in :

Rose , age 45, senior teacher, income 20 000 or over, living alone with 1 child, moored in a marina

I arranged a meeting with her in this town where Rose lives. She met me on the train station and we hit it off straight away, she was very chatty and informal and warm. She's got a daughter, Anna, who is 17 and who goes to university next year. I met her later, after we had the interview in a local cafe. This cafe was very lively and noisy, which is indicated in the text as [n]. They walked with me along the canal, all the way to the next train station, where I took the train back to Bristol.

[n]=noise

I = interviewer

P = interviewee (Rose)

I: What are peoples first reactions when you tell them that you live on a boat?

P: It varies. some people are quite open and think it's a really good idea. Some think that it is really romantic and other people just go "Oh my god, why are they not living in a house instead?" i think people are curious more than they are [pause] condemnatory or you know definite sense of outrage about it. It has been pretty mixed reactions. My parents both love the idea and they are both quite elderly have had a boat for quite a few years. They've never considered living on one [n]. My first boat was a sailing dinghy [details about the sailing dinghy she had as a child, unimportant details]. This is my second narrow boat. The first one I shared with my old partner [coffee arrives. croissants are served from a big plate]

I: Shall we have a little break or?

P: I don't know, I'm easy

[okay I continue then, this seems like a good moment]

I: Have you always lived on a boat?

P: No, we lived in a house for a quite long period of time. My first period of living on a boat ended when my daughter who is now 17 and started school. I've gone to university in Birmingham when Anna was a tiny baby and we struggled along with a derelict house. My then partner said "Well what's the point living in a house why dont you come to my boat instead?" Gradually we moved on from couple of nights to pretty much permanent on that boat. Until Anna went to school and intrigued things. One of the problems in the early 90s was that some started to view people living 'traveller style' lifestyle.

I: So they were not too happy about it?

P: There was quite an outrage at school whether Anna is living in a suitable environment. I kind of felt that we need to move back on to a house. We were contacted by social services and Anna was taken to hospital to have the general health check done. Our case was investigated and it was

lot of pressure. People were interested in Anna's health and they meant well [n]. I know in certain areas the vision would have been very different. things like 15 years later people changed quite a bit but still nonetheless people viewing living on a boat is [noise] children to be more subtle although in my experience [n] Anna grew up to be very happy and highly resilient and grew up to be such a wonderful kid [n] although probably not quite fit into a social norm of what a child should actually be like [n]

I: They might be people who don't know how it's like to be living on a boat?

P: people are quick to make judgements and I think there is a stigma attached to anybody who is seen as participating in a less than standardized lifestyle. many of us don't see the importance of material possessions that important to life but rather value the quality that living aboard brings to our lives. it's very difficult to see where they are coming from. I kind of do understand it, my father is a very conventional person and he just goes like:'well that's good then'. I can understand why people thought that way. it's probably still a slight stigma attached to living on a boat when you got kids.

I: Why do you think social services got interested?

P: I think it was because a four year old went to school and talked about her life on a boat. It got their alarm bells ringing. we lived in a centre of Birmingham where there was fairly alternative and probably less than legal lifestyle was presumed(?) ...I just think people were very alert to anything that was out of the ordinary. I have to say that anything other than that there was only support and understanding. and still there was all this questioning whether it was a suitable environment. Anna was then a very small child and she was undersize for her age but then she grew up to be 4ft 11 adult.she was never intended to be very big. people's attitudes are really quite strange as if there was a sense of "Ooh I wish i had guts to do that". There is almost an element of envy involved in it. The social service worker I was involved with said off the record that "you know, I think it's a great environment for a child. I think it will all turn out fine". It was pretty tough 13 months. But we kept the boat going for quite a few years and went for a quite a few long long weekend holidays. when i was doing my Phd. So we were still spending considerable amount of time aboard. We sold the boat when we moved down to the west country when i trained as a teacher in 1990 and since then really regretted it [selling the boat]. When my last relationship broke up we shared a house which we co-owned. I took my money out and bought a boat in which I moved in March this year. So we've not been on board this time for very long.

I: Aah

P: Long enough to work towards winter this year and I probably work in summer as well. It's good experience to get back on it. I love it. Anna is very comfortable and cats are getting use to it throughly. It takes a while to get use to living a life sideways again[laughter].

I: Have you got a permanent mooring then?

P: We have. We bought the boat through brokerage which came with a guaranteed mooring. It's not residential we are adept to number of nights which the marina pays per year. we stay the week in the marina and then the weekends we go out. I think it's one of those thing where everyone just turns a blind eye. There are quite a few people actually living in the marina If the authorities would try to get hold of it they'd say they're not too pleased. We pay mooring fees about £1600-1700 a year plus our insurance, which is slightly more for a liveaboard. But on the whole it's manageable. It's about the same as my mortgage would be if we buy house in this area [n]. By and large I'm always happier afloat than I am on land. and I have a long history of being surrounded by water [n]. My parents come from London and my father's family were ship wrights, working in the docks in London. My mother's family are Jewish and Irish. and so both sides my family have a long history of migration and being on water. As a family we all just enjoy splashing around water and being close to water if not on it [n]

I: Yeah. So what would you say was the deciding factor to move back on a boat? You mentioned something about lifestyle.

P: Hmh, I think it is just sense of easiness being on a boat. It's just a knowledge that I can just give up my mooring and go anywhere I choose where there is waterways. strangely enough, this might sound very odd, but I feel very constrained inside the house somehow I'm quite a recreative person and I feel kind of tied in one spot when I'm in a house. I think it's not a natural state for me to be in. It's because where I grew up. Just the idea that I can do something else in any point in my life. That really appealed. And I always thought that I can when I'm on a boat [n] I like the mental challenge that living on a boat brings to you, the things that g wrong on a daily basis [laughter] there is a saying it is just a job and it never gets shorter, but I know if I start doing it it will certainly get longer. I enjoy thinking things through. I like messing around with mechanics, and I put my hands up wit the electricity as well [n] it is just that mental intrigue that keeps me going. I'm not sure about the boater thing - opening a beer and sitting on a couch [n]. It can be quite hectic [n]. I dont want people to think me as a standard person, middle aged, 45 year old woman sliding into an old age. I'd reject that quite vehemently. That's the kind of sense living ni a house brings to me. That I'm suburban, middle aged, living out of occupation I suppose.. I don't want to do that. i think being close to water [pause] vitalises me in a way that living in a house doesn't.. it's not the actuality but the idea that i can close my eyes every morning and see a different tree. I can open my eyes every morning and see different birds or talk to different sets of people. So i think that was the deciding factor. Living in a house would constrain me in some way and I really don't want that.

I: Did you specifically choose this place when you bought a boat?

P: I realized quite quickly that finding a mooring in this area was going to be very difficult and I needed to be in a specific point cos Anna was still at school and I teach so I have to be more or less in a fixed point within a certain area I didn't want to go bridge hopping. I haven't abused it really. I tihnk in some cases people abuse the system. In other cases they think 'ooh this is great, you can do what you like really'. I'm aware of that.

I: If they are continuous cruisers?

P: Yeah..so there are continuous cruisers and people who stay in one place or maybe move couple of yards. that for me is not what boating is about. So, having come to grips with that i started looking around marinas to see what's available when it comes to moorings.BW said it is gonna be at least five years before i gain an online mooring here

I:Did they tell that in March?

P:No, that was about 15 months ago. I was off for the winter, at a winter mooring. we didn't except buying another boat then.This boat came up at Bashton marina. I have couple of friends who have also experienced boats. They came around. [The man who did a survey], a 75-year-old came out from the engine hole and said that the boat is gonna be really good.

I: You had a survey then?

P: Yeah. First boat we had we bought without a survey, simply because it never occurred to me that there could be anything wrong with the hull. I started scraping the hull I noticed that there is a lot of rust coming off the hull and hole sheets were lifting off. In fact my hammer almost went through the hull at one point. then I thought we need to sort out what is wrong with this boat, there was few problems with it. When we had it surveyed it was discovered that it was down to 1.7 mm plates, the hull surface.

I:Millimeters?

P: Millimeters. So from that point we had a survey done on it [n] It needed overplating.

I: Did you end up buying that boat?

P: We already bought the boat.

I: I see.

P:It's difficult when you see something and you fall in love with it. It was the first time we bought a boat, we had so many problems with it. When we bought this one I wanted to make sure all things were right. This boat was a lot more money than the first boat. Our first boat was £5000. It turned out to be a fine boat [n]. I learned a lot of lessons from that boat. This boat is much much larger and newer. I think with any boat there's going to be problems. tihs brand new boat I walked past this morning, really glossy, really pretty .absolutely beautiful. they got engine problems [n] Even brand new boats have problems. you just have to except it, it comes with a lifestyle really.

P: People usually think that living on a boat is incredibly cheap. "You lived in a house and now

you live on a boat. how cheap is that". But I think it costs. Not similar amount. I started predictive figures for a year and I worked out that it is probably going to be 400-500 pounds less living on a boat than living in a house. lot of things are the same. but yeah hmm [pause] I'm just amazed by the numbers of people who have moved on to a boat. They probably think it is cheap and then it turns out not to be the case. It's a learning experience [laughter]. It just goes on I think.

P: There's nothing in Finland that compares, is there?

I: No

P: You have house boats don't you?

I: I believe we have tugs because the sea freezes. I haven't actually been on the canals that much so I don't know. I live in Helsinki, I've seen tugs there. I've never heard anyone living on a boat.

P: I have friends in Holland who have lived all their lives on boats...when we lived on a narrow boat the first time one of [n] came over to see me. She lived on a dutch barge. It was quite big, about 25 metres and 4 metres wide. It's absolutely massive.

they came to look at my first narrow boat and couldn't get over how small it was and how narrow it is. That's the thing that always strikes people. You can touch the walls on your side [laughter]

I: How long is your boat now

P: 58ft, 17 metres, 2 metres wide. It is just a standard. Anna finds it funny that you can stand in the middle and touch both walls with your hands...

I: Why do you think people in general live on boats?

P: Some people combine it with this romantic idea that living on a boat is a fairly bizarre way to spend your life. Sometimes people are shocked how hard it can be - and they're quite shocked how lovely it could be early morning and late evening, it is absolutely stunningly beautiful. I think some move on boats cos they think it is a cheaper lifestyle. I think there is a lot of pressure on houses. If you like to be independent and own your own property that's well beyond reach for most of the people. I'm a teacher and I couldn't afford to buy a house and I'm 45. There are people who are younger than me who move on to boats because it is your own housing and who are quite romantically inclined and love the waterways. And older people who have retired and who's children have moved on to university and they wanna spend time on water. and for some people it is just a holiday alternative, just like renting a cottage. Go nowhere, do nothing. I think people do have variety of motives, sense of , romantic sense of freedom. But you're actually constrained by the waterways. you couldn't imagine a more rigid route way. Just longing to take a break from the business of life...

I: Couple of years ago there was this quite negative news coverage about people who live on boats. Do you think that might have put people of?

P: I think bizarrely it might have attracted some people [laughter] for reasons I can probably only guess.

I: Well I haven't really seen those articles, I was just told by other people

P: I think it was kind of a moral panic about travellers, a fear about people who don't conform, who don't ride the system. It was almost as a sense of anarchy in many respects. What we understand a normal life and quite often with the moral panic, the panic far outweighed the importance of a strike, if there was one. There can be negative views about people living on water. To my mind things have changed but not necessarily for the better. There is an outcry isn't there. Lots of values being on the water, sense of co-operation, a sense of community, we work together in order to survive. It's becoming more expensive and it's attracting people with a lot of money. It's a status symbol. It used to be the case that if you're in water it didn't matter what you were in. There was a sense of kindness and friendliness and generosity spirit towards each other. Even in my relatively new boat, it's only 13 years old, I had people pointing out that I should get it painted because that's not the kind of boat you want to be in the canal system. This is not how it used to be. I don't know if it was because I was in Birmingham where it's fairly cheerful in the early 90s and people just wanted to be out on the water just because for the sake of it, because they love the waterways and the heritage. And what it meant to people in respect people worked the system and whether or not it has changed significantly, becoming populated by people who see it as a status symbol.

I: Would you say there are classes then inside the boating community

P: There's strata even within boaters themselves. If you have a narrow boat as compared to a dinghy, everybody hates you and if you're in a GRP boat then you know that's to be [n] to. Lots of people get started with GRP boats, lots of people start out with dinghy or wooden sailing boats. It's rumbling around. The important thing is to be out in the water you know, get on and use it and look after it. And enjoy what it is and respect the history of different ranges. It will probably be less and less common as time goes on. People are wasting money all the time. That sense of maintaining that used to be such an intriguing and fascinating part of canal life seems to be out of the window. I have a problem with one of my windows so I went to see this guy. The guy said that I should have all windows redone, to remove the old ones and have new ones fitted. When I enquired the cost of that it really is a scary amount of money. That never used to be the way of living on a boat. You used to repair things. I'm horrified by this idea that you just buy a new one and throw the old one away. One of the other reasons I moved on a boat was that I want to leave less of a footprint [n]. When you live in a house and you look at what you throw away, what you buy and bring in to a house [n]. It's a terrific amount of consumption. I want to consume far less than I did. Whether I achieved that is another matter [laughter]. Too much time went on buying. It's about losing this idea of making a mend and repairing things. It's not healthy. This ties into a sense of materialism and consumerism.

I: Yeah. People do like to consume a lot, especially young people

P: My daughter is very bright. She's very socially aware. she's a tough cookie in lots of different ways. She likes watching television and I hate watching television. It's been an absolute delight on a boat that slowly her television consumption has swung. It's been an absolute delight watching it and just sitting quietly, with a book, doing work, looking out of the window, playing with the cat. Before when we lived in a house she was bored for the most of the time. She spent hours in a day watching television, just complaining about having nothing to do. as soon as we started living on a boat her television consumption has come down to maybe a couple of hours a week. I watched her the other night when she was preparing her jeans. She would never have done that if we'd be living in a house. I think the pressure would have been on her to ring one of her mates, go out, watch television, go around to someone's house for pizza That seems to be gone. her friends do come around the boat quite often. 17 year old boys they're vast glancing around all over the place. It's really quite nice. Anna is being a child rather than being a premature adult. I think that's another hidden benefit.

I: Definitely. What do you think other people think of people who live on boats?

P: I think it's pretty ambivalent. Mixture of envy, certain amount of disapproval I suppose. My mum said, she was discussing to one of our friends, they are of similar age, in their mid sixties. She said well your daughter has always been the one who got away, i think there is a sense of [n] viewing people who move on boats as slightly odd. but in some ways [n] strangling aspects of modern life. I think there is an element of envy. Then there is an element "I wouldn't want to live like that you know". Sometimes people judge boats by the outside: "They must be living in a squalor because there is stuff out on the roof and stuff on the back of the boat. They must be some sort of strange type of traveller hippies. They must be spreading anarchy. Disrespectful, unpleasant people". Would you like another coffee?

I: I'm actually fine yeah, I'm a really slow coffee drinker. But you go ahead.

[this was a bit of an episode, it was a table service, so it was a matter of getting a waitresses attention]

P: So yeah, ambivalence really. There are two ways of thinking about it. envious on the one hand and on the other hand they think : Well they live on a boat, they must be living in a squalor and segregation". I'm always intrigued by people's reactions but most of the time I think people just envy us. when Anna gives her address she's quite intrigued by people's reactions.

It's an element of showing off

I: Have you got a permanent address in the marina?

P: Kind of yeah. Post goes to the marina

I: Have you had any problems of not having a permanent address

P: We haven't had any problems. they are used to people living on boats, cos this is the longest established boaters community. by the station where you walked..they're happy to except boaters...where my parents live by the river there is a sense of boaters coming in and really living on their boats.

I: Do they live on a boat?

P: No, they've had boats but they live in a house. I think my parents would find it quite hard physically. My dad's been quite ill. When he came on board last weekend he was back in his position at the tiller. And everyone else just slotted onto the roles we had when we were kids. My

mum being charge of reading the map, I'm being charge of the ropes and Anna was given my brother's job which was handling the mooring pins. as she only weights about seven stones[laughter]. It was quite funny actually, we were like a piece of machinery. It's funny how you learn a role on a boat and you never really forget it. Well we were talking about people's reactions and lot of people say: I really envy you. that is just because they're not brave enough to try. My attitude towards boating was always that "well I try it and if i don't like, or we decide we're too old, then we'd do something different". I've always come back to boats. and I'll always see myself coming back to boats. It could be seen as my natural habitat.
[right, time to change a topic]

I: Do you get any paternalistic attitudes from men?

P: I do get like "Ooh, I wouldn't have done it that way" [laughter] or "Hmm, I see, that's interesting"

I: Yeah

P: Nearly all the men I've met have been really really sweet and they've wanted to help. I think there's a really strong ethos "men do the engines and women do the cooking' on boat world. But I think I'm a bit [?] . I'm a female boater living with a daughter on board. That's probably slightly unusual. However, two boats down from me there's E., who's 67, and she's been on board for 16 years and there isn't a job she hasn't attempted to do. She is really happy. she moved on a boat when her marriage broke down and she really enjoys her life. She's collected this group of men who do things for her, which is fantastic [I laugh]. There are advantages of being a woman you know and if you use it to get what you want. I don't have a problem with that. When we were buying a boat we found that lot of men were quite bemused by the fact two women, a woman and her daughter, came to look at the boat. They were like:"Well we got a really nice cooker, what else do you want to see" [I laugh, she is very entertaining]. Then I was like: "Lovely, lovely, but what I really want to see is the engine and see how it starts, have a look at the propellor, have a look at the hull". I've never seen anyone so shocked really, and then when I asked him to start the engine, he nearly fell through the floor [I'm just laughing-don't know if it is appropriate but I can't help myself] which was quite funny. I really haven't met anybody who's been less than helpful and interested in doing a job for you [n] There are paternalistic assumptions within men but they mean well. I like to be independent but sometimes i do need help. It's developing a sense of self knowledge. Some older people have 50 years of experience under their belt. G. was 75 when he came to survey my hull. I bet he knows more, far far more than I will ever know. And if he says something works better if I do it this way, then that's the thing to do it. I have nothing to loose by taking men's advice. I've got nothing to prove to anybody. I've got enough to do. They help me out with my electrics and wiring and I make new curtains for them. I'm fine with that, it works well for me. so I think you do have to except help. You need to understand that at some points you will need some help and equally there are some points where you have to offer help[n]. Give some, take some. sometimes i worry that what i offer back isn't as great as what i receive but i guess it balances it out in the end.

[Now finally, she gets to order coffee]

I: What sort of an advice would you give to someone who's moving on a boat?

P: Have a really good look around, we spent years.

I: Alright

P: We knew pretty much what we wanted. this time we did a survey done. Make sure you can afford it. And be prepared to embrace your experiences with open and fresh mind really. And be flexible and adaptable because nothing will be quite the same you perceived. I had the survey done...there will always be something you havent look into it. Being flexible about it and have some scope to deal with the problems when they occur. It's easy to get uptight. It's not the reason why most people want to go on waterway.

I: You said that you have a good sense of community by where you live.You said that many people have helped you and then you helped them in return

P: Yeah, I think that's one of the best ways about waterways. Waterways community is a sense of give and take. Then you pass that help forward. Doing something for one person feels really good. Or if somebody else does something to you. Life is about giving and sometimes about taking and if you make a good offer to people and you mean it and you help. that help comes back to you in some way. I think we should be living our lives more cooperatively and more thoughtfully with more generosity and time. This means a far more human place

I: Do you think there is more of "that" in boating world than housing world. Is there difference between these two?

P: In principle they should be exactly the same, but there is a difference. In winter you need far more help when you'd do in a house. Boaters are very individual people. They behave according to their own life and according to their own moral standards. They're not probably any higher or lower than in anywehre else really . There is something that unites people and that is living on water. I dont think you drift into it, you have to do it . People live on boats for variety of different reasons. those reasons [for them] are strong and valid ones. My experience of people moving on boats, this time and also last time is that it's a learning process and you have to be willing to learn. If you think you know everything [n]. I think some people who move on boats are very idealistic and very naive about what they're going to find and how they're going to deal with problems. And find that their life is rapidly descending into squalor. And they need to sell their boat to move back on land. It's actually quite difficult to sell a boat. And in the meantime the housing market has moved on and everything is pear shape.

I: Are you planning to continue living on a boat?

P: Yep, for the foreseeable future. My daughter goes to university next year. I might stay down here for few more years. I work in middle management at school so I have a relatively well paid job. Doesn't seem that way when the pay day comes. But it is relatively well paid. In this school, I really like. I can live in a beautiful place and at the moment, there is no need to make changes. I know that I don't particularly want to live in a house. I feel like living on my boat [laughter]. I love my boat. I am going to love my boat. It is a home for me. House has never been any more than a house. Or a kind of status symbol: "Look how well I'm doing", whereas my boat is a place where I can feel happy. No desire to give it up, I love living on a boat.We have two cats.

I: Have you got any other points or comments?

P: [pause]

I: I think we covered quite a vast area [we laugh] thank you very much.

P: My pleasure .How are you getting on with finding people to interview?

I: I've found eight so far

P: Do you think women rather than men are keen to talk about their lives?

I: Yeah definitely. I've got this little questionnaire [I hand her the questionnaire]